

A PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS OF NYĀYA-VAIŚEṢIKA'S
PADĀRTHAS AND ARISTOTELIAN CATEGORIES

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Abstract:

The purpose of this paper is to show the Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika theory of category is at par with the Aristotle's theory of category. I have straight way rendered the Vaiśeṣika term '*Padārtha*' as 'Category'. For, as I shall try to show in the course of my argument the Vaiśeṣika doctrine of '*padārtha*' runs parallel to the Aristotelian doctrine of 'categories' in all essential aspects. It is important to note right at the outset that the parallel is not to be carried beyond Aristotle. For, in the course of the development of philosophical thinking, the term 'category' has freed itself of its original setting and yet has written its specific significance. such is not the case with the Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika term '*padārtha*'.

Key Words: *Padārtha* (Category), *Upādhi*, *Anyatām bantaḥ* (Extreme otherness), *Abhidheya* (Designating names), *Abhidhāna* (Designation names), and *Sattā*.

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Introduction: Tarkasaṃgraha of Annambhaṭṭa states the doctrine in a categorical manner as: substance (*dravya*), attribute (*guṇa*), action (karma), generality (*sāmānya*), individual (*viśeṣa*), inherence (*samavāya*), and absence or non-existence (*abhāva*). They are the seven *padārtha* of Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika. The statement of Tarkasaṃgraha is chosen here to enunciate as it alone seems to mean to be the faithful to the original thought. The statement of Annambhaṭṭa carry the sense that the seven as mentioned above are the categories. In other words, these categories are posited. The statement of Annambhaṭṭa as a point, and that is to enunciate the Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika doctrine as such, where are, other statement of the doctrine, as for example, in the Saptapadārthī of Śivāditya, seen to as a loss to it, often thereby depriving it of its regard.

This loss of regard in the statement of the doctrine is seen into two ways. Wherever the statement of the doctrine posits as the *padārtha* themselves, the list of *padārtha* is not qualified by 'only'. But such a statement as used as descriptive means for the *padārtha*, as for example, *upādhyayaḥ* as in Saptapadārthī, the list is made to end with the restricted 'only'. This difference is brought out clearly in the

Nīlkaṇṭhī, a commentary on Tarkasaṃgraha-Dipīkā by Nīlkaṇṭha Bhaṭṭa. He says that the *padārthas* are the ways in which the signification of differences is determined. Bhāṣkarodayā written by Śrī Lakṣminṛṣimha Śāstrī, which is a commentary on Nīlkaṇṭha-Bhaṭṭa's Tarkasaṃgraha-Dipīkā-Prakāśa or Nīlkaṇṭhī, is even more explicit. It describes the *padārtha* as *upādhi* but takes care to explain that these predicative names signify extreme otherness (*anyatām bantaḥ*) and for this reason are called *padārtha*. It goes further and asserts explicitly that 'seven' is not a qualitative determination, but relates to our apprehension of the specific character of the differences.¹ Dipīkā commentary of Tarkasaṃgraha of Annambhaṭṭa follows this cue and says: the 'seven' speaks for the scope of the otherness and as that these seven-fold determination of otherness should be spoken of more positively as the seven types of distinctness (*vyavaccheda*).

Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika system uses the term 'padārtha' in a technical sense. Naiyāyika who is trained in original text is averse to rendering the term 'padārtha' as 'category'. The doctrine of the *padārtha* is a characteristically Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika position, and the adoption of the term by other

system of Indian thought only results in divesting the position of the strict significance, as we will see later. The fact that each school takes a different stand regarding the number and also the names of the *padārtha* should be reason enough to have to draw a line between the notion of *padārtha* and the specific doctrines based on it. It is imperative to attend to determine the notion first.

The *Dipikā* alone seems to make the point that the '*padārtha*' is in the first instance 'a name' in the sense of a designating term (*abhidheya*); and that the characteristic mark (*lakṣaṇa*) of a *padārtha* is that it can be named (*abhidheyattam*). It is but obvious that the reference to names here is not a proper name as for example 'Ram'. While speaking of designating term, it is important to note the distinction between two ways of designating. Elementary logic speaks of uniquely descriptive names as designations. Such descriptive words are meant to identify to the individual and are closer to proper names in their denotative capacity. The *Dipikā* has in mind still another meaning, where the meaning signifies a notion. It is a way naming with a cue to determining the meaning of the term used. The *padārthas*

are called '*abhidheya*' and not '*abhidhāna*'. *Abhidhā* is a descriptive name given to things already identify as individual. The implication of the term '*abhidheya*' is that the thing, rather the notion it names, is not yet distinctively apprehended and that it is the naming that is both to signalize and to signify it. It could be possible to mark the two apart by speaking of *abhidheya* as designating or signficatory names and of *abhidhāna* as designation or significant names.² The point that the distinction lies in the intended reference in the two terms, the implied reference, in *abhidheya* being to the function of naming, whereas in '*abhidhāna*', it is to the result achieved. If the term '*abhidheya*' can be granted to have a distinctive connotation, then it should follow that to describe the '*padārtha*' as a list of nameable objects or as a classification of knowable things as seems to be the common practice, is to say the list, a misleading way of explicating the notion. A nameable object or a nameable thing is blanket term which could be used of everything that in any manner forms a part of our conscious experience. Neither expression permits an exclusive application, and that list of all two *padārtha*. The *padārtha* are names, but not of what is

ordinary parlance is called things for objects. It is even more important to note that the list is not a classification either.

It is a point to note that neither Nīlkaṇṭhī nor the Dipīkā both of which explicate the notion of the *padārtha* by the conception of 'name' speaks of 'object' but only of 'terms' (*pada*). Besides each of them makes it clear that the name aspect is only an explicatory conception, not the main part of the notion. The Nīlkaṇṭhī remarks that name or a term (*padābhidheya*) is an additional of a *padārtha* and it is intended to remove a sort coming if any such is involved, a naming the *padārtha* originally under seven heads by virtue of their forms such as *dravya* etc.³ The Dipīkā breaks up the term '*padārtha*' into two: the '*pada*' and '*artha*' as standing in a genitive relation and it immediately acts that 'the meaning of a term' is only the etymological sense of the term '*padārtha*'. The sense of the 'only' is that the *padārtha* in their basic distinctions are apprehended independently of any such connection with the term '*pada*' and '*artha*'. The point of these denials of Nīlkaṇṭhī and the Dipīkā could be construed as followed: '*padārthas* are objective distinctions and are not to be reduced to the linguistic or conceptual moods of our understanding. It

is unfortunate that none of the other Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika commentators seems to have pursued either of the two points made by Nīlkaṇṭhī and the Dipīkā, namely, the *padārthas* name distinctions and the *padārthas* are names of terms.

The first position implies a definite metaphysical standpoint. The explication of this point depends upon an analysis of the concept of 'being'. In both these respects, the Vaiśeṣika and the Aristotelian systems so a parallelism. Any kind of doctrine of categories is similarly absent in any system of thought that goes under such a name as materialism or naturalism on the one hand and idealism or spiritualism, and phenomenism on the other. Or, reductive metaphysics, that is a way of thinking which reduces diverse types of being to someone order, can strictly speaking have no place for the doctrines of categories, as names for the distinct moods of being. Reductive metaphysics reads the words in terms of 'plurality' only and seeks a principle of unity that would explain away the plurality. This way of thinking, by-and large, suffers from the fallacy of over-simplification and for that reason ends up by separating the reality it firms from the world of experience. But, for a philosophy which would find the

reality within the world of experience, 'diversity' is a fact which is basic to plurality. It is not suggested that the metaphysics of plurality and of diversity always remain a part. Yet, in spite of the fact that historically the coalesce in different periods in various degrees, the remain characteristically different in their logic. Plato and Aristotle who stand in a historical relation to, offer a good illustration. It is Aristotle who advocates the doctrine of categories, being concerned with the problem of 'becoming', that is with the way of a thing comes into being, and not Plato, who is concerned to find 'pure being' and finds to be one absolutely. The doctrine of categories is possible, rather it is essential to a metaphysics which takes its stand on the fact of diversity. And both Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika and Aristotle are seemed to devote quiet some attention to determining the meaning of the term 'being'.

The Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika system draws its title from its main principle, namely, '*viśeṣa*' that is 'distinctness'. It begins with a statement of the *padārtha*; for the principle of distinctness makes it necessary to name the things that stand out in their diverse mood of being. Kaṇāda is explicit on the point of distinctness, he equates the

knowledge of 'tattva' with the capacity to comprehend the diverse *padārtha* named, in their similarities as their differences, by virtue of the distinct nature of each.⁴

Both the Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika and Aristotle distinguish different senses of the term 'being', differing somewhat in their approach though. Aristotle appears to start negatively, in that he arrives at age doctrine in the course of an attempt to remove the ambiguity from the term 'being'. The Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika speaks of, or rather straight away proceed to classify, the sense of the different words signifying 'being'. This is so, perhaps because Sanskrit has the advantage of being able to use the word 'being' unambiguously in its own form and in verbal or predicative form, and can even use the two together significantly. Aristotle feels called upon to clarify the difference senses of the word 'being' or common usage along the word to be used in the sense of 'real' in order to name the ways in which things are. In Greek, 'is', 'being', 'beingness' and 'beingly' from a group, so that 'Socrates is wise' or 'Socrates is a man' are genuine expression in Greek.⁵ This information enables us to see that the predicative 'is' central to the meaning of 'real' or 'reality' and no unwarranted transition is involved in

shifting from the one to the other. Further, it reduces the gap between the 'true' and 'real'. For 'true' is a fairly common meaning of 'real' in spoken or written Greek so that 'true' can be made applicable to thing and objects, although it applied primarily to propositions.⁶

The ambiguity is even greater in English. It is so because English admits two forms only of the verb 'to be', namely the present participle 'being' and the verbal expression 'is' and these two forms have to carry the sense of the extract noun 'reality', and the adverb 'really' and even of the adjective 'real'. It is obvious that the two sets of words do not belong to the same step, with the result that in English one can hardly see that 'real' and 'to be' and that 'is' in turn present the verbal on of 'real' or 'reality'.⁷

The doctrine of categories brings up yet another ambiguity in 'being'. In the Oxford translation of Aristotle's works the participle of 'being' is translated as 'what there is' or 'what exists', whereas the plural 'to onta' is translated as 'things that are' or as 'existing things'. Such a translation is felt to be unsatisfactory for it happens to diverse the plural from the singular. Even so, this in itself does not appear to mean to be ground

enough for an objection. For the principle 'being' and the plural noun do not stand on the same putting, not in the Categoria at least. The plural noun is used of 'things that are', in the sense of objects in the world of experience, that is to say, of things like, 'man', 'ox' etc. Whereas the participle noun 'being' is set to run parallel with 'unity' and they both in their distinct senses are set to be predicates of absolutely everything.⁸ It is of 'being' in the sense of 'things that are', such as 'man', 'aquatic' that Aristotle asks the question 'what are the things in themselves?'. For these things can be set 'to be': 1) in an accidental sense and 2) to by their own nature. The list of categories is in answer to the question, what are the essential kinds of beings as evidence in themes? It is the different senses of 'essential being' that are called the 'categories' or the 'figures of predication'.⁹

The Vaiśeṣika explication of categories is connected with their technical views of the term 'artha'¹⁰ in the sense of 'object'. Used in this special sense the term stands for- '*dravya*', '*guṇa*' and '*karma*' etc. Praśastapāda lays down that the name '*artha*' is to be used of *dravya*, *guṇa*, and *karma* only¹¹. It is the presence of these three that is indicated by the term 'artha'.

¹² What is meant by 'presence' here is that they are '*sattā*' that is they stand for the order of existence. For this reason, Kaṇāda had at one stage granted only these three categories. He was Gotama who extended the use of the name 'artha' to all perceptible substances and qualities. ¹³

The Vaiśeṣikasūtra not only means the '*padārtha*' in terms of '*sattā*' but they also attempt to determine meaning of the word '*sattā*' in his sūtra 1.2.7. This sūtra defines '*sattā*' in terms of '*sat*'. '*Sat*' is the present principle of the verb '*asa*' (to be). But '*sat*' gets used as a genuine noun that is as a name which is a pointer word. And it needs to be rendered in English as 'the real' in keeping with its nominal status, rather than by the abstract noun 'reality' as is done generally. In this sense '*sat*' is the concept of the metaphysician. He can use it in a non-comital way, and take up his own stand for naming and describing what to him is 'the real'. The word '*sat*' needs no further embellishment with the adjective '*parā*' ¹⁴ meaning 'supreme' as in the case of other words conveying the sense of being or knowledge, like '*parāsattā*' '*parāsāmānya*', '*parāvidyā*'. The word '*sat*' also has a settled meaning in language as 'good' and in that sense functions as an adjective with a

normative or evaluative connotation. '*Satya*' (the truth) is a noun derives from '*sat*' with the meaning 'having the property of being sat'. '*Satya*' stands for 'truth' as for 'true being', that is for 'truth in knowledge' as for 'the real'. '*Satya*' is defined by Pāṇini as that in which, the seer of the truth, the object and the perception of truth cannot be conceive in another way. ¹⁵

Further, as can be seen from Vaiśeṣikasūtra 1.2.7 'the sat' is to be judged as '*sat*'. Vātsyayana too includes the perception of the '*sat*' as '*sat*' in the definition of a principle. ¹⁶ According to this sūtra which stands just as '*sat*' or 'the real' in substance, attribute and action is to be called '*sattā*'. Viśvanātha elaborates the point more in his Bhāṣāpariccheda. He says that what the Vaiśeṣika calls the '*parāsattā*' or '*parasāmānya*' is the way of being (*ṛtti*) as *dravya*, *guṇa* and *karma*. 'The *sattā*' stands for the generality of different moods of being and can be said to signify the order of existence in general. This view borne out by the further criteria let down for determining the meaning- come-application of the word. They are two. The first is a direct apprehension (*pratyaya*) of it as '*sat*' and the second is the dealing with it in the same manner (*vyavahāra*). The expression of

the apprehension in language being classed along with the latter. The Bhāṣya to Vaiśeṣikasūtra 1.2.4.¹⁷ adds that the criteria are based on the ground of the distinction, that is, the irreducibility between substance, attribute and action. The next Vaiśeṣikasūtra 1.2.8 lays down that there is no 'sattā' other than in these three forms. Vaiśeṣikasūtra 1.2.4. has used another verbal noun in the definition of 'sattā'. 'Sattā', according to this sūtra, is 'bhāva'. 'Bhāva' is the abstract noun derived from the verb 'bhū'. Meaning of 'bhū' is 'to be'. 'To be' is to be understood in the sense of 'coming to be in time'. 'The sattā' can be said to stand for the general order of the existence, while 'bhāva' signifies the being in the sense of actuality in that order. The word 'bhāva', like sat, is used more as a genuine noun rather than as an abstract noun. 'Bhāva' in this context stands for the necessity towards actuality involved in the nature of 'being'. The conception is elucidated as – that which is to be followed up. That is to be affirmed in its way of being (*anuvṛtti*), and not as being a separable (*vyāvṛtti*). Hence 'bhāva' no special name. It is further explained by *vyāvṛtti* as the 'paratva' only and not *aparatva* of *sattā*.¹⁸ The Bhāṣya simplifies the conception of *bhāva* as the being itself

of the reals, that is, of all that are sat. 'Bhāva' is said to belong to all the objects (*artha*).

'Sat', 'sattā' and 'bhāva' form a gradation. Sat stands for 'that it is'. In other words, 'sat' stands affirmed independent of any predicative concept. Hence the assertion 'sat iti' is called knowledge or a true apprehension.¹⁹ 'Sattā' stands for the order of existence and admits of a feature. The distinct type of *sattā* is given their names like *dravya* etc., but the order stands expressed in its generality only. For this reason, it is expressed by the abstract noun 'paratva' and not by a verb. 'Bhāva', the elucidatory concept of *sattā*, can be expressed by an existential predicative expression 'vidyate'²⁰ and expresses the occurrent aspect of 'being'. However as applicable to *sattā* it is still affirmation in general and therefore admits of no distinctive name²¹. A name presupposes an object of a specific character because of which the distinction between the general and the individual can go with a name. Hence the distinction is said to appear with *dravya*, *guṇa* and karma²² for their distinctive modes of being.

This brief linguistic survey could be said to set out in perspective the

metaphysical background for a doctrine of categories, as it marks the parallelism between the Vaiśeṣika and the Aristotelian doctrines. Such a doctrine implies a three teared view of being: 1) sat (the real) corresponding to what Aristotle calls 'being qua-being', 2) 'sattāḥ' in the sense of the order of existence corresponding to what Aristotle calls 'the essential way' in which things are, and 3) lastly the individual things such as man, pot, etc. The doctrine of categories in both these systems is metaphysical only to the extended to which they grant the notion of the real. For they do not raise it into doctrinaire system. This kind of, what may be called, and open notion of the real, alone can grant the order of existence to be a distinct conception or a distinct level of knowledge. Another equally important feature of this conception of the real is that, it denies two individual things, taken in their individual setting even the right, so to speak, for the order of existence in its generality. In this its last feature is non-empiricistic in its outlook. The kind of metaphysics involved in a doctrine of categories is rationalistic realism. It maintains that the order of existence is marked by diversity, and the categories just name these diversities. Western thought

succeeds in preserving this infuses on diversity, for Aristotle embodies it in his logic. In the Indian tradition, the Nīlkaṇṭhī and Bhāṣkarodayā explication of the categories as expressing distinct differences (*anyatam vantaḥ*) fails to make its mark under the over powering influence of the Nyāya conception of *upādhi*. For the same reason, the point that the *padārthās* are names gets lost sight of.

Aristotle at his list of categories from more than one angle we have already considered his approach to the problem from the cite of things. The other approach is linguistic. He distinguishes expressions in language into 'simple expressions' that is names and 'composite expressions' that is predictive expressions and declares that "expressions which are in no way composite, signify: substance, quality, relation, time, position, state, action or affection". From the side of things these same names are called 'figure of predication'. The seeming opposition, perhaps more so in the eyes of Sanskrit scholars, between categories as 'types of beings' and categories as 'figures of predication' should disappear when the two conceptions are bridged over by the conception of the 'types of meaning'²³.

Aristotle speaks of the three interchangeably. Aristotle's approach is linguistic, not verbal. He considers 'name' and a name is a term (pada) and not just a word. Both words and terms are connected with meaning essentially, but in different ways. A word singly or in a group is called a 'term' only when it is used to make a statement with. A term, therefore, is defined by its function, as either the subject or the predicate that is as either the naming or the attributive or described expression in a statement. A word is a symbol and means what it stands for by a linguistic convention. A term means by way of its syntactical function and hence is said to signify rather than to mean. The Nīlkaṇṭhī and the Dipīkā speak of the *padārthas* as names or terms and as the meanings of terms respectively, most probably purposefully. For, Vātsyāyana gives a clear statement of the nature of a term (pada). A word in Sanskrit in its inflectional or only is to be called 'a pada' and divested of its inflection it ceases to be 'a pada'.²⁴ According to Vātsyāyana the basic inflections are two: naming (*nāmiki*) and describing (*ākhyāti*)²⁵. The purpose of a pada is the apprehension of its significance, as for example, the term 'cow' can signify the individual or the species or

the form. That is to say, the same word means differently according as it is used either as subject or as predicate or in a still more abstract sense even. The manner in which a term is intended is by and large understood in language communication. But if, what a term signifies is to be explicitly express, it could be readily observed that the mode of signification can be indicated only by using it as the predicate of the term used as a naming expression. The name of a term is on a different footing than the name of a thing as already seen. The former is a designative name while the latter is a referential or a pointer name. The two kinds of names function differently in statements. Hence it could be maintained that categories as names of terms could be express predicatively only. On that score the Aristotelian 'figures of predication' do not in any way differ from the *padārtha* that is as names of terms or even as meanings of terms.

Conclusion: It needs to be stressed that Aristotle himself describes the categories as 'figures of predication' and not as 'predicates'. Although the categories have generally come to be spoken of as 'first predicate'. It is of 'being' and 'unity' that uses the word 'predicate', but qualified as

universal, in the sense of 'predicates of absolutely everything'. The categories are not the same thing with either these universal predicates or with predicates in the ordinary sense that is attributive predicates. The latter express specific determination of their subjects in judgements. Amongst the terms used attributively of a subject, general nouns, as for example man, pot and adjectives, as for example wise, blue function as class terms in a way in which verbs and adverbs cannot. In his logic of inference Aristotle texts into account only the class aspect of predicates. It is most probably by some misunderstanding of Aristotle that the Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika *padārthas* are sometimes explained as 'a classification of things'. It needs to be emphasized that the conception of classification is incompatible with a statement of distinctness, for all classification amounts to a unification in terms of some common character. Even apart from this consideration, the notion of a category cannot be rendered by the conception of a class. The word 'class' is used primarily of empirical concept. All common or general noun, as for example table, sparrows, are class-words. Similarly, 'red', 'great' may be used in the sense of 'red

things' or 'great men' that is to stand for classes. Our understanding of the class-word or the general noun lies the ones mentioned above arises in the course of our experience of individual instances of the kind. The conception of the class depends upon the notion of quality as characterising and the notion of the individual as in some way characterised. The class comprises of members which need to satisfy some common quality or qualities. The members of a class are characterised by similarity in respect of that quality or qualities which makes them all under the same class. The class-word is primarily the name of a common character which for ordinary purposes is used to name both the class of individuals or the individuals in the class. Logically speaking the class-word is a description, that is, it is a predicated which is applied to the individuals. For this reason, it is not necessary for us to have observe every individual in a class. Modern logic represents a class by a function. In the expression 'Px', 'P' is a predicate variable and 'x' is an individual value. So, when we say 'Priyanka is a girl', 'girl' stands for predicate and 'Priyanka' stands for individual.

A category word, 'substance' for example, is not a class-word like 'man' or 'sparrow'. The category word '*guṇa*' even is not a class-word like 'sound' or 'colour' etc. For, the tights of objects distinguished in a category are marked by diversity, unlike the members of a class which are marked by a common character. Each of the nine substances listed by Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika is distinguished by its own characteristics marks yet, they are all named '*dravya*'; for each is apprehended as being of a pattern, a pattern which is judged to be the seen irrespective of the varying character of the objects. A category is the same name used of diverse types of objects displaying the same mode of being. The class concept is educated to explain plurality, but diversity needs another concept to account for it and that is the concept of a category. A list of categories is therefore a list of diversities. In the first instance the diversities are only named, for names mark differences in a way in which no other expressions do. A name implies a counterpart, which is not a contradictory, in the form of 'the other' or 'another'. Hence categories come primarily to be presented as names. That they are designating names is an account of the category names. That designating names

stand for patterns, or forms, distinguishes them from denoting names which stand for things. The Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika thinkers expressly refer their categories to '*sattā*', the order of existence as distinguished from the things in the world like, pots and garments judging by Vātsyāyana's account of terms and the Nīlkanthī-Dīpīkā comments on how the *padārthas* are to be construed, the Nyāya-Vaiśeṣika *padārthas* who would have been described as 'figures of predication' as in Aristotle.

Notes and References:

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